

Impact of Copper(II) chloride in Barium titanate on its structural and optical properties

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Abstract

Copper (II) chloride is doped with barium titanate (BaTiO_3) for different weight percentage by sol-gel and hydrothermal method. The impact of doping copper (II) chloride on the structural and optical properties of BaTiO_3 is studied. XRD reveals tetragonal phase structure of BaTiO_3 nanopowder with traceable amount of impurities. Copper (II) doped BaTiO_3 nanopowder possess distorted tetragonal symmetry which is determined by the changes observed in its c/a ratio. SEM and TEM images confirm change in the morphology with the increase in the dopant concentration. UV-Vis absorption spectrum and PL spectrum exhibits the characteristic peak of BaTiO_3 for all the samples and exhibits blue shift on the addition of copper (II). The FTIR spectrum provides the details on the functional group and frequency modes of Raman spectrum confirms the presence of tetragonal symmetry for undoped BaTiO_3 and distorted tetragonal phase for copper (II) doped BaTiO_3 . The non-linear optical properties were compared for the doped and undoped barium titanate nanopowder.